

Statistical Physics 2005:

**Modern Problems
and New Applications**

Annual Conference in Ukraine

August 28–30, 2005

Lviv, Ukraine

Book of abstracts

Synergetic economics of the manufacturing firm with mass production output

V.P. Demutskiy (1), O.M. Pignastiy (2)

(1) Karazin National University 31, Kurchatov Str., Kharkov, 61108,
E-mail: demutskie@mail.ru (2) ISF "Technology" 10/12, Kotlov Str.,
Kharkov, 61052, E-mail: techpom@online.kharkov.ua

Statistical Physics essentially expands the field of its application, it penetrates into such closely-related fields of knowledge as chemistry, biology, meteorology more and more. Statistical Physics is one of the main instruments which could be useful for description of system's self-organization in the comparatively new field of knowledge, called "Synergetic Economics". The application of the methods of Statistical Physics for its description is possible owing to the representation of the manufacturing firm with mass production output in the capacity of the system with numerous quantity of elements (the basic products) of stochastic nature, being in the production process. Conduct of the basic products lengthwise the technological chain depends on the definite manufacturing and technological laws in accordance with the technological process of the manufacturing firm, its production plan, the availability of manpower and equipment. The state of the production system's basic products at any time moment is given as the point in the two-dimensional phase space. The function of the basic product's distribution in the rate of expense's variation is set and the equation having analogy with the kinetic equation in Physics is put down here. The engineering and production function, which is analogous to the force moving the basic product lengthwise the technological chain of the production process, is given and can be determined with the help of technical documentation of the article's manufacture approved in the manufacturing firm. The generating function describing the interaction of the basic products (the system's elements) during their moving lengthwise the technological chain of production process with technical equipment, is based on the equipment disposition schemes and its technical characteristics according to the schedule of the workpieces machining. The closed system of balances equations for the moments of distribution function is put down here in the zero approximation with the small parameter, with the usage of the kinetic equation. The system of balances equations describes the conduct of the basic economical macroscopic rates of the production system, such as process stocks, pace and dispersion of the production output lengthwise the technological chain. With the help of the balances equations the well-known relations of the business operation theory used for the calculation of stocks and pace of the production output were obtained.

Sokolovsky S., 112, 174-176
Soldatov A.V., 57
Soldatova E.D., 177, 178
Solovyau V.B., 104, 190
Sorokov S.I., 105, 179
Sovyak E.M., 180
Stasyuk I.V., 49, 181-183
Stelmakh O.M., 190
Stepanenko D., 184
Stetsiv R.Ya., 185
Strecha J., 66, 113
Stupka A.A., 173
Suchorski Yu., 106
Sukhanov A.D., 76
Sushko M.Ya., 186
Svylzinsky A., 163

Tchalbagysky Z., 157
Tokarchuk M.V., 65, 131, 132, 133, 142

Щорічна конференція в Україні
“Статистична фізика: сучасні проблеми і нові застосування”
Львів, 28–30 серпня 2005 р.

Програма і тези доповідей

© Інститут фізики конденсованих систем НАН України
Львів, 2005

Комп'ютерне макетування: Андрій Швайка
Укладання: Олег Величко, Йосип Гуменюк та Олеся Мриглюд

Vdovych A.S., 103, 179, 183
Velychko O.V., 183

Верхольняк Т., 81
Vikhrenko V., 81
Vil'ova G.K., 162

Voloshinovskii A., 114
Vorobyov O., 78, 192

Формат 84×108/32. Ум. друк. арк. 10,4.
Друк офсетний. Тираж 200 прим.

Друк: ТзОВ “Ю.М.І.”, 2005